

PLURAL EXPRESSION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article is about very important matter of English language which is regarded to the singularity and plurality of the languages Uzbek and English. Besides, there are some examples of differences of two languages are analyzed.

Key words: Comparative study, singular and plural categories, plural suffix, unique to some languages, the -s suffix, -es, -ies or -ves suffixes

The essence of everything is manifested in the process of organizing by comparing related objects and events.

Comparative study of languages is also an interesting and important issue in linguistics. There are many similarities and controversies between not only fraternal but also non-fraternal languages.

Thanks to independence, the international relations of our republic have improved. This marked the beginning of a process of renewal, change, and change in language and literature. It has led to an increase in the interest and attention of our people to the English language.

Language is a social phenomenon. It changes, renews, and evolves along with society. The uniqueness of languages is also related to the mentality, psyche and, of course, the beliefs of the people. On some issues of this aspect, we would like to consider the example of the expression of the plural in English and Uzbek.

The singular and plural categories belong to the noun phrase, which represents quantity. In English and Uzbek, the singular form of horses is expressed without any suffixes or means.

For example: kitob - book, o'quvchi - pupil, talaba - student, qalam - pencil, daraxt - tree, qush - bird and others.

In English, we add the suffix -s to many nouns to create a plural form. For example, if there is a book in the unit, it is enough to add the suffix -s to make it plural: books, pupils, students, pencils, trees and others. The Uzbek suffix -s is translated as "-s".

However, not all words are added the -s suffix to make a plural. Some words which ends with -s, -ss, -sh, -ch, -x, or -o have the suffix -es added to make a plural.

For example: bus- buses, watch - watches, box - boxes, dish- dishes, glass - glasses, potato - potatoes, torch - torches and so on.

In Uzbek, numbers are also used to express the plural. In that case, the suffix "-s" will be dropped. In English, on the other hand, the suffix "-s" or "-es" is used when the noun comes with a plural number:

one flower - two flowers,
one zebra - four zebras,
one lion - three lions,
one apple - six apples,
one book - five books,
one pencil - eight pencils,
one computer- twenty-five computers,
one chair - fifty chairs and others.

At the end of the word, we add the suffix -ies, dropping the letter y on nouns with a consonant and a letter y. For example: one baby - two babies, one butterfly - two butterflies, one lady - three ladies, one strawberry - five strawberries, one cherry - seven cherries and so on.

However, if the letter ends with a vowel and y, then the suffix -s is added. For example: toy - toys, boy - boys, key - keys, monkey - monkeys and others. The plural form of most nouns is based on these rules.

Additionally, if our word ends in -f / -fe, we drop -f / -fe to create the plural and add -ves instead. For example: leaf - leaves, knife - knives, wolf - three wolves, scarf - seven scarves and others.

However, there are some nouns that do not follow these rules. We call them irregular plurals. They have their own plural form, so we need to use the same form, not the -s, -es, -ies or -ves suffixes. For example: one man - two men, one mouse - three mice, one person - six people, one child - eleven children, one sheep - two sheep, foot - feet, goose- geese, tooth- teeth, fish - fish, deer - deer, woman - women and others.

It would be a mistake to add -s to the words in this list. It's a good idea to memorize this list of words. They are not many.

In Uzbek, the suffix -s also means respect. For example, "Daddy came." (Dadamlar keldi) In English, however, this is not the case.

It is known that in Arabic the plural is formed as a result of internal inflection. For example, secrets (sir-asror), news (xabar-axborot) and so on. Such words are widely used in Uzbek, but this phenomenon is not suitable for pure Uzbek words. In English, there are many words that form a plural as a result of internal inflection: colf- colves - thigh, thief - thieves - thief, and so on.

In English, although some nouns are in the plural, they represent the singular. For example, chess, news, measles, methods, and so on.

In the Uzbek language, although it comes in the plural, there are almost no words denoting unity, only in a few foreign words: information and so on.

In English, more plural adjectives are added to express the meaning of the plural in the words given above. In the Uzbek language, such a phenomenon can be observed in compound nouns, that is, words such as people, nation, although essentially plural, are expressed in unity. When they are added to a plural suffix, they denote the plural and denote related objects or events. For example, nations, armies, nations, and so on.

It is also possible to form a plural by repeating some words in Uzbek. In this case, the repeated word corresponds to the numerative or arithmetic word. For example, a box - box drawers (sandiқ-sandiқ sep), a cupboard - a bookcase (javon- javon kitob), and so on. The appearance of the plural in this form is often characteristic of conversational and artistic styles. In English, however, it is difficult to observe a particular situation.

One of the peculiarities of the Uzbek language is the formation of the plural by the longer pronunciation of vowels. For example: people (o'dam).

In conclusion, the expression of the plural is unique in English and Uzbek, and the differences depend on the development of the language and society, the mentality of the people, the characteristics of the sister and non-sister languages. Comparative learning is also very important in language teaching. A clear goal is achieved by paying special attention to aspects that are unique to some languages.

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